

MODERN AND ANTHROPOCENTRIC APPROACHES TO PUNCTUATION RESEARCH

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Annotation: this scientific article will consider the features of punctuation and an example of their modern traditions. Also, dwell on punctuation marks on it separately.

Keywords: traditional approach to punctuation, modern approach to punctuation, anthropocentric approach to punctuation, development of the punctuation system.

As previously seen in the paragraphs, the traditional punctuation system can be fully formed on the basis of European writing in the late XIX and early XX centuries. In linguistics, three main stages are distinguished in the formation and development of punctuation theory:

- 1) traditional approach to punctuation-period from the XV to the middle of the XX century;
- 2) modern approach to punctuation-period from the mid-XX century to the late XX century;
- 3) anthropocentric approach to Punctuation – the period from the end of the XX century and the beginning of the XXI century to the present.

The traditional stage of punctuation research coincided with a period in almost all linguistics and played an important role in the popularization and strengthening of general punctuation standards. Scientific study of punctuation - early theoretical views on the history of punctuation M.V.Lomonosov, R.Lounch, Dj.Robertson, N.I.Grech, A.X.Vostokov, F.I.Buslayev, K.F.Becker, W.I.Klassovsky, Y.K.Groth, W.Day, J.Angus, J.K.Nesfield, G.McDonell, M.Spencer, H.V.Fowler, J.Damouretta, A.M.Peshkovsky, L.V.Sherba, R.It found expression in the school and scientific grammars of the skiltons. In European languages, the basic principles of the development of the punctuation system are based on the development (hierarchy)of general functions of punctuation marks. While the initial views relied on their task of separation – separation and grouping of textual parts, later identification of sentence fragments and their position (position)in the sentence structure was seen as the main criterion. By the beginning of the XX century, the division of punctuation into text, the arrangement of punctuation within a sentence, had brought to the surface their various classifications. Including,

- 1) signs that apply singly (comma, dotted comma, hyphen, two dots, many dots) and in pairs (two dots, hyphen, bracket and hyphen) between the sentence;
- 2) at the end of the sentence are single (dots, interrogative and exclamation marks, many dots) and double (brackets and quotation marks).

It should be noted that in almost all linguistics, theoretical issues of punctuation were studied in the context of punctuation practice, language teaching methodology in relation to orthography. It is known that any linguistic interpretation acts on the basis of a product of speech belonging to a certain period. Therefore, the formation, improvement of punctuation traditions, the popularization of certain rules, the strengthening and regulation of general punctuation standards, firstly, the practice of punctuation – the activity of creators, writers, scientists operating in this language, and secondly, the methodology of teaching the native

language as a component of national writing, that is, the education of the native language, and thirdly, the mission of ensuring written literacy of Preliminary work on punctuation in the above-mentioned, European languages, in particular Russian-M.Smotrytsky, M.V.Lomonosov, Y.K.The grammar of the Grots was of a purely practical nature and was based on the teaching of the scientific norms of the language – punctuation, orthographic rules-at school. Likewise, in Uzbek linguistics, the first punctuation views were carried out within the framework of language teaching methodology, along with orthographic norms. In the works of intellectuals of most nations – linguists, jadids, enlighteners, active in the first half of the last century, these two tasks were carried out in a harmonious state under the initiative to literate the nation, teach the norms of spelling, correct pronunciation, cultivate a culture of speech. In Particular, Fitrat, S.Mutalibov, S.I.Ibrahimov, Z.M.Marufov, O.U.Usmanov, K.In textbooks and manuals, articles and dictionaries of minors, thoughts on punctuation are considered within the framework of literary language norms (spelling, pronunciation), native language (syntax) teaching, writing (Alphabet), speech culture.

At the next stage of the development of punctuation marks K.F. Becker's The main theoretical backbone of theory of logical syntax as well as the application of punctuation - related to the methodology of language teaching, the controversy over the priority of syntax, semantics and intonation-took a leading place. These discussions have generated various point-of-view views in defining the foundations of punctuation in linguistics. In Particular, F.I.Buslayev, S.I.Abakumov, A.B.When defining the theoretical basis for the use of punctuation, such as Shapiro, semantics is a focus on the content of a sentence, i.e., in favor of linking the use of punctuation to meaning, S.Bulich, N.Grech, Y.K.Groth, Sh.Shoabdurahmonov and others interpret the syntactic construction of syntactic – written speech in the definition of punctuation rules, or rather, the use of punctuation marks, depending on the construction of the sentence. Some theorists, such as L.V.Shcherba, A.M.Peshkovsky, K.F.Becker, L.A.Bulakhovsky, H.Rustamov and others try to explain in connection with the role of intonation – punctuation in the expression of the tone of speech and rhythm. In this process, it also did not go unnoticed in different linguistics which of these aspects is given more priority. In Particular, V. Klassovsky explained the semantic basis advantage in the system of applying German and Russian punctuation marks and contrasted them with the English, Italian and French punctuation system, which relied on a syntactic basis.

Later, universal possibilities of punctuation began to surface, which did not obey the current norms. For example, aspects of punctuation such as hyphenation, two-dot, dotted comma began to be clarified in texts of different styles, such as the occurrence of different functions, interchange of places, meaningfulness, variability, polifunctionality. This set the stage for new approaches to punctuation research.

The modern stage of the study of punctuation marks falls into different periods in different linguistics. The formation of private - stylistic norms of these punctuation marks, in addition to the general – traditional norms that exist in most languages at the same time, is, moreover, a process associated with the development of the national language.

In the second half of the XX century, most languages would undergo spelling reform, including Russian and the former tributary national languages (1956) that it dominated. Within the framework of spelling issues, it was also possible to approach punctuation not from a modern – purely linguistic point of view, but in methodological, didactic, psychological, communicative, stylistic, poetic, semiotic aspects. Attention began to be paid to such issues as

situations complicating the regulation (codification) of punctuation standards, the expanding methodological capabilities of punctuation in fiction, the desire of creators to create a style through the individual application of punctuation marks, normalized and unregulated author punctuation. In World linguistics, the first attempts to do this were made by S.I. Abakumov, A.B. Shapiro, A.A. Reformaty, I. A. Boduen de Courtene, L.G. Vedenina, N.S. Valgina, D.E. Rosenthal, N.N. Barulina, D. Crystal, M. Garrett, K.F. Meyer, B.S. Schwarzkopf, G. Newnberg, M.V. Parkes, N.R. Branigan, B. Begins with the jobs of the jouns.

Even at this stage of punctuation, the tradition of approach within the framework of the methodology of teaching the literary language norms characteristic of the initial stage in scientific interpretations – graphic, orthographic, punctuation (syntactic) norms, that is, native language, was preserved. In Particular, O.S. Chekanskaya, V.G. Dubrovin, N.S. Valgina, W.A. Itskovich, A.I. Nikerov, L.V. Vvedenskaya, B.I. Osipov, D. This can be clearly seen in the work of the eytchisons.

During this period, considered an important stage in the formation and development of the discipline of Uzbek punctuation, H. Goziyev, G. Abdurahmanov, K. Nazarov, Sh. Along with the pure linguistic studies of the shoabdurakhmonovs, a number of practical works related to the field were also carried out within the framework of spelling and syntactic teaching. In Particular, Z. Marufov and Y. Abdullayev's "a collection of syntax and punctuation exercises", K. Nazarov's book "can you write right?", "Punctuation in separated sections", "Uzbek sign-spelling rules", "H. Rustamov's" syntax and punctuation teaching methodology", G. Abdurahmonov's "tablits from punctuation", "methodology for teaching punctuation", H. The scientific articles, textbooks and manuals of Gafurov, such as "intonation and punctuation issues in Atov sentences", carried out practical work within the socio-political, cultural needs of their time

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